

ISLAMIC FINANCE: FEATURES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The article discusses the fundamentals and trends of the development of the system of Islamic finance, the principles of Islamic financial institutions, as well as financial instruments that are used within the Islamic financial system. The distinctive features of Islamic and traditional banks are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the problems and prospects of the development of the Islamic finance system.

Keywords: Islamic finance, Islamic financial instruments, Islamic financial institutions, Islamic bank, ethical finance.

Introduction

Recently, there has been an increasing interest in the topic of the functioning of the Islamic financial system, which is dynamically developing and gaining more and more confidence in the global financial space. The number of Islamic financial organizations and institutions is constantly increasing, new Islamic insurance funds and companies are emerging that are actively developing their activities in non-Muslim countries. The activities of Islamic financial structures are becoming more diverse and complex. The capabilities, potential and competencies of Islamic financial organizations in organizing and supporting large-scale transactions are expanding [1] (Azaryan, 2012). The phenomenon of intensification of the growth of Islamic finance in the period of increasing globalization and against the background of the global crisis requires an explanation of the occurrence of this phenomenon.

"Religion is a powerful force, and the nature of its impact depends primarily on what feelings it inspires and what actions it inspires...". The potential inherent in Muslim religious teachings is slowly but surely influencing the changing picture of the global financial market. The functioning of the Islamic economy, which is based on the system of Islamic finance (SIF), is regulated by Muslim law. The basis of Muslim law is the Sharia, which can be considered a universal system of social regulation in normative terms and which is based on two groups of sources, the Koran and the Sunnah [15] (Syukiyaynen, 2008). The basic principles of the functioning of the Islamic finance system include the prohibition of riba, garar, meisir and haram. According to Sharia, riba, a pre-determined interest rate on investments or an increase expressed in other quantities that is not related to returns and does not involve labor costs, is prohibited [7] (Litau, 2016). This is mentioned in the Qur'an: "Those who take a vengeance will rise up on the Day of Judgment, just as the one whom Shaitan turned into a madman with his touch will rise up. This is their punishment for what they said: "Truly, trade is the same as profit." But Allah has allowed trade, He has forbidden usury. If an admonition from Allah comes to any of the moneylenders, and if he acts according to this admonition, then his past sins will be forgiven him."

The prohibition of riba is due to the fact that usurious activity does not lead to the creation of a product and the growth of the welfare of society. Profit-making is welcome in Islam, but the principle of social justice insists that receiving remuneration or incurring losses should be in accordance with the contributions of borrowers and lenders. How does the prohibition on interest payments manifest itself in practice? It is prohibited:

- any increase in the size of the loan or the accrual of loan interest, including in the case of overdue debt by the borrower;

- charging fees in excess of the actual costs for processing and servicing the loan; обращение circulation of bonds of all types, including those with a zero coupon. эм issue of credit cards in case of accrual of interest on the amounts provided on credit. начисл accrual of interest on all types of deposits in banks with the exception of deposits of trust investment. Garar implies the presence of excessive uncertainty or ambiguity of the terms of the contract arising from a lack of information and control. Garar can be considered the sale of questionable goods, unknown goods or at an inappropriate price; goods without an accurate description or preliminary verification; nonequivalent barter exchange of goods, etc. [2] (Bekkin, 2010). Garar invalidates the contract. A high degree of uncertainty in modern financial activity is characteristic of insurance and derivatives transactions. Therefore, from the point of view of Sharia, such transactions are considered invalid. It should be understood that any business activity contains a certain degree of risk and uncertainty. But only excessive uncertainty invalidates the contract, and excessive and unjustified risk invalidates it. Accordingly, based on this principle and the prohibition of Gharar, the system of Islamic finance cannot be subject to such crisis phenomena as the mortgage crisis in the United States, default in Russia in August 1998. Meisir in Arabic means "gambling", is unconditionally prohibited by Islam. Meisir also includes unearned casual income. In a broad context, it can be considered as a ban on the movement of funds for the purpose of their expanded reproduction without creating a real product. What is characteristic of the modern financial system.

Haram, translated from Arabic, means "sin" and is a ban on conducting or participating in activities related to the distribution of obscenities, alcoholic beverages, the manufacture and sale of idols, the provision of services to pagan temples, gambling, etc. Thus, Sharia prohibits financial transactions related to the

sale of weapons, alcohol, tobacco products, pornography, pork production, taking bribes and lending money at interest. The rules of the Islamic finance system prohibit "speculative" behavior, unjustified risk, uncertainty and gambling, since the income received as a result of such activities does not lead to a real increase in the well-being of society [18] (Shibanova-Roenko, Saidov, 2011). CIF is also based on such principles as the requirements of the inviolability and fulfillment of contractual obligations, the parity distribution of risks, the fair distribution of wealth and income, the balanced pursuit of economic well-being and social justice. Compliance with moral norms, social justice, acting within the law, moderation in spending, censure of monopolization of markets are the fundamental foundations of Islamic economic activity [7]. The formation of the system of Islamic finance takes place not only within the framework of economic and financial relations of subjects, but also extends to the ethical, moral, social, cultural and religious spheres in order to strengthen equality and fair distribution of benefits throughout society. Therefore, the implementation of the CIF model is possible in the context of Islamic teachings on ethics, the distribution of wealth, social and economic equality, and the role of the state. Thus, the principles of the functioning of the Islamic finance system do not contradict the fundamentals of a market economy and do not have serious disagreements with traditional European and Russian socio-cultural values. Despite the fact that the principles of Islamic financial activity were enshrined in religious and legal sources many centuries ago, the concept of "Islamic finance system" (SIF) is relatively new and has appeared in scientific circulation since the mid-1980s. Foreign and domestic researchers [1, 2, 3, 9, 17, 19] (Malinovskaya, Skobeleva, Brovkina, 2012; (Sharafutdinova I.R., Kulakova S.A., 2014; Kabir Hassan, Kayed, 0) are of the opinion that the system of Islamic finance focuses on the maximum distribution of risks, which contributes to the formation of a close relationship

between finance and real economic activity, the dependence of the level of profitability of financial activity on the level of profitability of the real sector, and not vice versa. The functioning of the CIF leads to financial stability and stability, income growth and employment, and as a result – to a reduction in poverty. To achieve these results, it is necessary to meet and have such conditions as a developed financial system, the primacy of the law, legal institutions that protect the interests and property rights of investors and creditors; quality management and political will; trust in the government. The application of a set of Islamic rules and regulations is a reinforcement of these conditions. Thus, the system of Islamic finance is a system of financial organizations and regulatory institutions, mechanisms for conducting transactions, financial instruments regulated by Sharia law. Taking into account modern realities, it should be added that the need for an Islamic financial model in the context of globalization is significantly increasing. Globalization leads to increased interdependence of the economies and financial systems of different countries of the world. The emergence of crisis phenomena in one country inevitably leads to financial or economic shocks in other countries and regions. Islamic finance has proved its resilience during the recent crisis.

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